

IDENTIFICATION OF IMPACT DAMAGE ON A SANDWICH PLATE THROUGH NON LINEAR ELASTIC WAVE SPECTROSCOPY (NEWS) USING WAVELET ANALYSIS

M. Meo¹, G. Zumpano
*Crashworthiness, Impact and Structural mechanics group
School of Engineering Cranfield University
Cranfield, Bedford, UK MK43 0AL*

ABSTRACT

In order to reduce the problems related to the detection of impact damage in composite structures, the development of new methodologies capable of localising and assessing impact damage are necessary. A possible answer at this problem is offered by an evolution of the Non linear Elastic Wave Spectroscopy (NEWS), a methodology developed for geophysics applications.

The NEWS damage detection based technique consists in the analysis of spectrum of a signal acquired from the structure under investigation excited by a bi-harmonic signal. In pristine condition, the signal spectrum presents two picks at the excitation frequencies. In presence of damages, the material starts to behave non-linearly around the damage location, this behaviour shows up in the bi-harmonic excited signal spectrum as side bands of the excited frequencies. The magnitude and the number of the side bands are related to damage size and magnitude. In this study, experimental findings on a sandwich plate were compared in order to understand the sensitivity of the NEWS technique to impact damages. The results showed that the proposed methodology was capable of localising successfully the presence of impact damage and impact location and it can be used as a first assessment of the presence of damage in aircraft application where the presence of damage should be quickly estimated. Further research studies and methodology development are needed to assess the location, the magnitude and the type of damage.

KEYWORDS: Non linear Elastic Wave Spectroscopy, harmonics, sidebands.

INTRODUCTION

In order to increase the structure safety and to reduce maintenance cost by early damage detection, aircraft industries are steering the development of non-destructive testing techniques.

¹ Phone: +441234750111 ext.5220 Fax: +441234752149
email: m.meo@cranfield.ac.uk

Nowadays, a great deal of consideration is given to the development of damage detection techniques based on linear acoustics within a predictive maintenance program. Usually, the damage presence and severity are estimated by acoustical linear techniques, analyzing wave speed changes, damage reflected waves, and/or amplitude changes. However, a new promising NDT class, based on material nonlinear elastic wave behaviour [1-9] monitoring, is under investigation. The advantage of nonlinear elastic wave NDT based techniques is their larger sensitivity to damage than linear elastic based techniques [1], so as early signs of material degradation can be detected long before linear acoustic properties change. The theory background of nonlinear elastic wave propagation is based on the concept of nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity [1-2]. In presence of such nonlinear mesoscopic units caused by damage presence, the structural dynamic response shows different behaviours with the change of the excitation load. In particular, when a sample is excited simultaneously with continuous waves of two separate frequencies, frequency-mixing spectral components are generated such as harmonics and the sum and difference of the excitation frequency waves (sidebands). This behaviour is clearly identifiable in damaged materials but hardly measurable in undamaged materials. This makes the monitoring of these phenomena, an effective method to detect micro-damage in aircraft composite materials. However, the methodology has yet to be developed and applied to aircraft composite structures and much work is needed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the methods and the easy-of-implementation in a structural health monitoring system. This paper investigated the capability of the proposed techniques to detect the presence of impact damage on an aircraft sandwich panel. Impact damage is an important issue, since striking foreign objects on composite structures may cause small undetectable damages for the current inspection technologies, and under in-service cyclic loads might degenerate in a premature catastrophic failure of the structure.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A sandwich section of a firewall of helicopters, which consisted of a Nomex 6.35mm thick and Hexcel AS4-8552 laminates was analysed. The plate dimensions were 380x253x2mm plate (Figure 1-a), and it was simply supported across the short edges. The equipment configuration is schematized in Figure 1-b.

Figure 1 – a) Test panel b) Equipment configuration

A piezoelectric transducer was used to generate the low frequency and the high frequency wave. The transducer was driven at the bi-tone sine wave ($f_1=7400\text{Hz}$ $f_2=384\text{kHz}$) by a TTi waveform

generator. The plate response was acquired by a broad band AE sensors (Figure 1-a), digitalized by a Tektronics oscilloscope with a sampling frequency of 5MHz and stored using 250kpoints. The acquired signals were averaged 40 times before being stored in order to minimise their noise content. The damage was introduced by impacting the sandwich plate with a sharp object, yielding to a visible hole of 1mm diameter and 5mm deep. Various acquisitions were carried out by modulating the bi-tone excitation signal and by keeping constant the voltage of the low frequency sine (10Vpp) and modulating the voltage of the high frequency sine wave (384kHz) from 20Vpp to 7.5Vpp.

RESULTS

The plate dynamic response was analysed from a stationary point of view by evaluating the acquired signal power spectra using wavelet analysis [13]. The reason for the adoption of wavelet analysis over Fourier analysis can be found in the uncertainty principle [10]. According to the uncertainty principle, the frequency ($\Delta\omega$) and time resolution (Δt) are related by the following inequality:

$$\Delta t \Delta \omega \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad (1)$$

This means that for Fourier transforms the higher the time resolution, the smaller the frequency resolution. Therefore, in order to have both high frequency and time resolutions long time lags have to be acquired and stored. On the other hand Wavelet Transforms (WT) can guarantee a higher frequency resolution than FFT and the possibility to analyse the time-frequency evolving of the signal using shorter signals with a consist savings of storage memory.

WT linearly decompose an arbitrary signal $s(t)$ by projecting it on functions that are simply dilations and translations of a parent (or mother) wavelet $g(t)$ via the convolution of the signal and the scaled/shifted parent wavelet.

$$CWT(a, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(\tau) g^* \left(\frac{t-\tau}{a} \right) d\tau \quad (2)$$

where a is the dilation parameter and τ is the translation parameter.

Morlet wavelet [11] was selected as mother wavelet. This choice was determined by their analogies with the Fourier transforms expressed by its equation:

$$g(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi\gamma}} e^{-\frac{t^2}{\gamma}} (\cos(\omega_0 t) + i \sin(\omega_0 t)) \quad (3)$$

Basically, the Morlet wavelets are a Gaussian-windowed Fourier transform, with a central frequency $f_0 = \omega_0 / 2\pi$ and the width of the gauss curve (the wavelet frequency band) γ . The central frequency f_0 was determined by the frequency resolution Δf , requested for the signal processing (in this work $\Delta f = 1\text{Hz}$), and the maximum frequency f_{max} of interest as showed below [12]:

$$f_0 \geq 2\alpha \frac{\left(\frac{f_{\max} + \Delta f}{2} \right)}{2\pi\sqrt{\gamma}\Delta f} \quad (4)$$

with α larger than 2. The CWTs were evaluated on a portion of the recorded signals 5 times longer than the time period of the low frequency excitation signal. To reduce the computational time of the CWTs, the acquired signals were evaluated in two frequency windows (Figure 2, Figure 3). The low frequency window was defined between 0.9 and 3.5 times the low excitation frequency (7400Hz). The high frequency window was defined by a frequency range between -5.5 to 5.5 times the low excitation frequency component centred at the high excitation frequency component. By analysing the high frequency windows (Figure 2-b and 3-b), time end effects [12] are clearly identifiable; therefore the CWT decomposition was not taken into account in these regions in both the frequency windows investigated.

Figure 2 – TF representation of CWT coefficient amplitudes for a 7.5V high frequency excitation amplitude: a) Low frequency window; b) High frequency window.

Figure 3 – TF representation of CWT coefficient amplitudes for a 20V high frequency excitation amplitude: a) Low frequency window; b) High frequency window.

A series of harmonics of the low frequency component of the excitation as well as sidebands of the high frequency component were easily identified (Figure 2-3). The amplitude changes of the harmonics and sidebands at the different excitation load are shown in Figure 4. The amplitude for the low frequency component of the excitation showed a decreasing behaviour with the increase of the voltage of the high frequency (Figure 4-a). The consequent energy loss was compensated by the increase of the odd harmonics (Figure 4-b). In particular, the 3rd harmonic amplitude fitted a quadratic polynomial as predicted by the theory for purely hysteretic material (Figure 5-b). The plate response amplitude at high excitation frequency component increased with decreasing rate

with the excitation voltage. The deriving energy loss was compensated by the growth of its sideband amplitudes (Figure 5-a).

By observing the behavior of the first left and right sidebands (Figure 6), it is possible to note that the curves follow the classical two-fold nonlinear interaction between f_1 and f_2 with their amplitude proportional to $\beta \cdot A_1 \cdot A_2$. As shown in Figure 7-a, the experimental second sidebands resulted bounded by the curves $\alpha A_1 A_2$ and $C(\beta, \delta) A_1^2 A_2$, where α is a measure of material hysteresis, $C(\beta, \delta)$ is a function of classical nonlinear coefficients β, δ and A_1, A_2 are the signal amplitude at the frequencies f_1 and f_2 . These curves reproduce the second sideband behaviour for pure hysteretic material and classical nonlinear material respectively [14]. The experimental second sidebands tended to be closer to the classical nonlinear material curve (for small high frequency response amplitudes), while for the largest amplitude investigated the response deviates from it tending to the hysteretic material behaviour. A similar deviation from the classical nonlinear behaviour with the increase of the high frequency response amplitude was given by the first sideband (Figure 7-b). This showed that damage introduced in the sandwich plate introduced both classical nonlinear and hysteretic behaviour, where the hysteric contribution increases with the excitation load.

Figure 4 – a) Amplitude at the excited frequencies; b) 7400 Hz sine wave harmonics

Figure 5 – a) 384 kHz sidebands; b) 3rd Harmonics behaviour

Figure 6 – (a) Comparison of 1st left and right sidebands with the classical nonlinear behaviour

Figure 7 – (a) Comparison of the second left and right sidebands with the hysteretic and classical nonlinear behaviour;

CONCLUSION

This paper presented a damage detection investigation carried out using Nonlinear Elastic Wave Spectroscopy (NEWS). The methodology is based on the observation of the presence of harmonics and sidebands on the spectrum of acquired signal excited by a bi-tone signal. In pristine conditions, the signal spectrum did not present any harmonic or sidebands, which were recorded on the damaged signal spectrum. The harmonic and the sideband amplitudes highlighted behaviour compatible with the theory. The overall results showed that the proposed approach is capable of detecting the presence of damages on sandwich composite structure, even when this is contained in a small area, and it is hardly visible as for low velocity impact damage.

REFERENCES

1. K. Van Den Abeele, P. A. Johnston, A. Sutin, Nonlinear elastic wave spectroscopy (NEWS) techniques to discern material damage, part I: nonlinear wave modulation spectroscopy (NWMS), Res. Nondestr Eval, pp. 17-30, 12 (2000).
2. R. A. Guyer, P. A. Johnson, Nonlinear mesoscopic elasticity: evidence for a new class of materials, Physics Today, April 1999, pp 30-36.

3. P. Johnston, The new wave in acoustic testing, *Materials World* Vol. 7. No. 9, pp. 544-46 Sept 1999.
4. L. A. Ostrovsky, P. A. Johnston, Dynamic nonlinear elasticity in geomaterials, *Rivista del Nuovo Cimento*, Vol. 24(7), 2001.
5. K. E. –A. Van Den Abeele, A. Sutin, J. Carmeliet, P. A. Johnston, Micro-damage diagnostics using nonlinear elastic wave spectroscopy (NEWS), *NDT&E International*, Vol. 34(2001), pp. 239-248.
6. K. E. –A. Van Den Abeele, J. Carmeliet, J. A. Ten Cate, P. A. Johnston, Nonlinear elastic wave spectroscopy (NEWS) techniques to discern material damage, part II: Single-Mode Nonlinear Resonance Acoustic Spectroscopy, *Res. Nondestr Eval*, pp. 31-42, 12 (2000).
7. K. E. –A. Van Den Abeele, J. De Visscher, Damage assessment in reinforced concrete using spectral and temporal nonlinear vibration techniques, *Cement and Concrete Research*, (2000), pp. 1453-1464.
8. K. Van Den Abeele, K. Van De Velde, J. Carmeliet, Inferring the degradation of pultruded composites from dynamic nonlinear resonance measurements, *Polymer Composites*, Aug 2001, Vol. 22.
9. M. F. Hamilton, *Nonlinear Wave Propagation in Mechanics*, AMD-77, The American Mechanical Engineers, New York (1986).
10. L. D. Landau and E. M. Lifshitz. *Theory of Elasticity*. Pergamon, Tarrytown, NY (1959).
11. P. J. Loughlin, L. Cohen, The uncertainty principle: global, Local, or both?, *IEEE Transactions on signal processing*, Vol. 52(5), 2004.
12. S. Mallat, 1998. *A wavelet tour of signal processing*, London: Academic Press.
13. A. Kareem, T. Kijewski, Time-frequency analysis of wind effects on structures, *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, Vol. 90, pg. 1435, 2002.
14. M. Meo, G Zumpano, X. Meng, E. Cosser, G. Roberts, A. Dodson, Measurements of dynamic properties of a medium span suspension bridge by using the wavelet transforms, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, Nov 2004.